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Factors Influencing Technical Efficiency among Small Scale Sesame Farmers in Central Taraba State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to identify factors influencing Technical Efficiency among small scale Sesame Production in Central Taraba State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to describe the Socio-economic characteristic of the Farmers, establish the technical efficiency of Sesame farmers in the study area and identify factors of technical efficiency of famers in the study area. Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Purposive and simple random sampling techniques were used in selecting 82 sesame farmers who were interviewed as respondents using structured questionnaires. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and stochastic production efficiency frontier. The results revealed that males constitute the highest (64.6%) proportion of the respondents. About (48%) of the farmers were within the age bracket of 31- 40 years, among sampled households. The mean age of the respondents was 42 years, while 63.4% were married. The result further indicates that about 90.2 % of the respondents were literate at least having one form of formal education or the other with 70.7% have household sizes that are more than six with a mean of about 9 persons. Over 81% had 6-20 years of Sesame farming experience, with 10 years as the average. Access to extension services remains a challenge, as over 80% lack access to the study area. Most of the respondents (76.8%) lack access to credit. The result of the stochastic production efficiency frontier indicates that variables Seed, farm size, labour and herbicide were positive and significant at 1% 5% and 10% level of probability and hence play a major role in Sesame production in the study area. The coefficient of age, farming experience, household size, access to credit and membership of cooperatives were significant and therefore, increases technical efficiency which agrees with a prior expectation. It was concluded that the majority of Sesame farmers were relatively technically efficient in their use of resources, with a mean technical efficiency of 0.81. It was recommended Sesame farmers do not realize their full production potential, there is a need for sustained improvements on performance through enhanced roles of extension agents by the government in educating farmers on new technologies, which will significantly raise the technical efficiency.

Keywords: Sesame production, small scale farmers, technical efficiency, Central Taraba

1.0 Introduction

Agriculture is the driver of Nigeria's economic development. Its role in the provision of foreign exchange and development of economies cannot be overstated, as it remained for a long time the main machine for the earnings (Nkamleu, *et al.*, 2010; Adeniyi and Ogunsola, 2014). In Nigeria, the sector contributes 42.1% of the current GDP (Eleri *et al.*, 2012) with more than half of Nigeria's population currently employed in the agricultural sector (Manyong *et al.*, 2005), and with the vast majority of these individuals living in rural areas. The sector remains in the hands of small-scale farmers who use traditional methods and rudimentary tools of production, resulting in unsustainably low crop yields despite their high commercial and export potential. Evidence has shown that the majority of the population in most rural areas are small scale farmers providing food for human consumption and raw materials for export and manufacturing industries (Mbah, *et al.*, 2016).

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Determining the factors influencing technical efficiency status of Sesame farmers is very important for policy purposes. In an economy where technologies are lacking, technical efficiency studies show the possibility of raising productivity by improving efficiency in the use of existing resources. Most empirical literature dealing with farm technical efficiency, at least in Nigeria, has been concerned with the measurement of technical efficiency by using production function, profit function, or stochastic production frontier model as analytical techniques (Omonona *et al.*, 2010). The application of DEA is still scarce in Nigeria. Only a few studies have employed it (Ajao, 2011; Jatto *et al.*, 2012). This study intends to depart from the more common analytical approaches by using the DEA approach to estimate the factors influencing technical efficiency among small scale Sesame farmers in the central part of Taraba State.

Sesame seed is an important component of Nigeria's agricultural export (Chemonics, 2002). It currently ranks second to cocoa in terms of export volume in Nigeria and is fast becoming prominent among non-oil exports because it is one of the few cash crops that can earn the country foreign exchange. Available records show that Nigeria exported 140,800 tonnes of sesame seed worth \$139 million in 2010. It was also recorded that Nigeria earned ₦210 billion from the export of sesame seed products in the first half of 2012 (Ciuci, 2013). This increasing demand for sesame seed provides Nigeria an opportunity to increase its production to meet the international demand for the commodity. The realization of the potential of sesame production in the acquisition of foreign currency for the country made increased production of the crop a prominent priority in the Agricultural Transformation Agenda of the Federal Government of Nigeria (NCRI, 2012).

Sesame is one of the cash crops grown in the central part of Taraba State. It is a very popular crop among rural farmers in the area. Despite all attempts to increase the production of sesame in Nigeria, the average farmer still produces only at a subsistence level, using the traditional system of farming and low-yielding varieties. Research has been carried out on other crops but there is no information on the productivity as well as lack of pertinent research findings on the technical efficiency of the Sesame farmers in the study area and to identify the factors influencing efficiency levels among farmers. Assessing the factors influencing the efficiency of farmers may be one of the ways that help to improve the performance of sesame production in the area. In this regard, this present study is an attempt towards analyzing the factors influencing the technical efficiency of the farmers in the study area and aims to bridge the prevailing information gap on the contextual factors contributing to technical efficiency differentials and sources of inefficiency in the production of sesame.

1.1 Objectives

The broad objective of this study was to analyse the factors influencing technical efficiency among small scale Sesame farmers in the Central part of Taraba State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. describe Socio-economic characteristic of the Farmers;
- ii. establish the technical efficiency of Sesame farmers in the study area and
- iii. identify factors of technical efficiency of famers in the study area.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The study was carried out in the Central part of Taraba State, Nigeria. The central part is made up of five Local Government areas (Bali, Gassol, Kurmi, Gashaka, and Sardauna) and one special Development Area (Ngada). The area lies roughly between Latitudes 10° 31' and 7° 18'N, longitudes 10°18' and 11° 37'E of the Greenwich Meridian. Kurmi is bounded in the north by northern Taraba state, south-west by southern Taraba and south-east by the Republic of Cameroon. Its area has a land mass of 33,689 km² with a projected annual growth rate of 3.5% which brought the population figure to 969,189.96 people as of 2016 (Taraba State Government (TRSG), 2016). The area lies on the south-east border with Cameroon and these areas are richly blessed with fertile soil which grows a number of cash crops and food crops such as Sesame, Bananas, Plantains, Rice, coffea arabica, Tea, Groundnuts, Pear, Palm trees, Cocoyam and Cocoa. Others include Maize and Guinea corn. Agriculture is the mainstay of the inhabitants engaging over 75% of the population for local consumption and the rest exported, either to other parts of the country or outside the country. The area is also endowed with

various natural resources including precious stones like gemstones, Forest, Waterfalls and Mountains. It is the only area that favours the production of highland Tea in Nigeria.

2.2 Sources and Type of Data

Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. The primary data were collected with the aid of a well-structured questionnaire, containing information such as the socio economic characteristics of the respondents (age, level of education, household size, etc.) and information on farm characteristics such as farm size, farm experience, inputs, and quantity of output used by the farmer were collected.

2.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A multistage sampling technique was employed for the study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of two Sesame growing local Government (Kurmi and Bali), from the five local Governments that make up the Central zone of Taraba. The second stage involved the random selection of three major Sesame producing villages from the selected LGAs, and finally, Sesame farmers were selected in proportion to the number of Sesame farming households in each village is the highest Sesame growing villages. In all, 82 Sesame farmers were sampled for the study.

2.4 Analytical Technique

Descriptive statistics were used to address the socioeconomic characteristics of Sesame farmers while the Stochastic production frontier was used to determine the technical efficiency of the farmers.

Battese and Coelli (1995) presented the stochastic production frontier as:

$$Y_i = f(x_i, \beta) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where, $i = 1,2,3,\dots,n$, Y_i = output of the i th firm, X_i = vector of input, β = vector of parameter to be estimated.

But the stochastic frontier function has two error terms, V_i and U_i , unlike the traditional production function (Amaza and Olayemi, 2002).

The technical efficiency (TE) of the production of the firm is defined as the ratio of the observed output (Y_i) to the corresponding stochastic frontier output Y^* . Mathematically,

$$TE = \frac{Y_i}{Y^*} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

$$Y^* = \exp(x, \beta, v_i) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The Empirical Model

The Cobb-Douglas stochastic frontier production function is specified as;

$$\ln Y_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_{1ij} + \beta_2 \ln X_{2ij} + \beta_3 \ln X_{3ij} + \beta_4 \ln X_{4ij} + \beta_5 \ln X_{5ij} + V_{ij} + U_{ij} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where,

Y = Output of Sesame farmers (kg)., X_1 = quantity of seed (kg), X_2 = farm size (Hectares), X_3 = labour (Mandays), X_4 = quantity of herbicide (litre), X_5 = quantity of fertilizer used (kg), $\beta_0 - \beta_5$ = regression coefficients to be estimated.

V_{ij} = normal random errors assumed to be independently and identically distributed, having $N(0, \delta^2)$, U_{ijs} are the technical inefficiency effects which are assumed to be independent of V_{ijs} such that U_{ij} is the non-negative truncation (at zero) of the normal distribution with mean U_i and Variance $\delta^2 v$ where U_i is defined by;

$$U_i = \delta_0 + \delta_1 Z_{1i} + \delta_2 Z_{2i} + \delta_3 Z_{3i} + \delta_4 Z_{4i} + \delta_5 Z_{5i} + \delta_6 Z_{6i} + \delta_7 Z_{7i} \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where,

U_i = Technical efficiency of the i th farmer, Z_1 = Age of the farmer (years), Z_2 = level of education (number of years spent in school), Z_3 = farming experience (years), Z_4 = household size (number of persons), Z_5 = access to extension services (yes = 1, no = 0), Z_6 = access to credit(yes = 1, no= 0), Z_7 = membership of cooperative (membership =1, otherwise = 0), $\delta, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_7$ = coefficients and unknown parameters to be estimated.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Socio-economic Characteristics of the farmers

The socio-economic characteristic of Sesame farmers in the study area is presented in Table 1. As typical in African farm households, males constitute over 64.6% of the household heads while 35.4% were women. This further buttresses the fact that Nigerian agriculture is still male dominated, implying that men have more access to the resources and information required to produce crops more efficiently than their female counterparts

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(Fasoranti, 2006; Otitoju and Arene, 2010). The majority of the farmers were within the age bracket of 31- 40 years, constituting 48% among sampled households. The mean age of Sesame farmers was 42 years. It is evident that most Sesame farmers are aged. This would likely affect the efficiency of the farmers in the study area. Several studies have reported that the aging of the farming population is a source of concern for production efficiency (Ojo *et al.*, 2009; Ogunniyi, 2011). In rural communities, marriage is a respected and prestigious institution that bestows social status and recognition of people. The results showed that 63.4% of the respondents were married, 23.2% were single and 13.4% were widow/widower. The high proportion of the respondents who are married is an indication that family labour could be available for sesame farmers in the study area. The result of this work is in line with the findings of Abu *et al.* (2011) and Rahman *et al.* (2009) who reported that a high proportion of married respondents would contribute widely to the use of family labour by the households as the wives and children constituted the labour force. The result indicates that about 90.2 % of the respondents were literate at least having one form of formal education or the other. This implies that the potential for increased sesame production since education help farmers to have access to information on new agricultural innovation which enhances their productivity. IITA (2002) reported that the level of education attained by farmers to a large extent determines the farmer's level of adoption of new innovation without difficulties which in turn increases their farm output and subsequently the profit obtained by the farmers. About 70.7% have household sizes that are more than six with a mean of about 9 persons. This implies that households are excessively large in size, which could serve as a source of family labor. Over 81% had 6-20 years of Sesame farming experience with the average years of experience of 10 years. It is thus, reasonable to infer that farmers in the study area are well experienced in farming sesame and depicts good signals for higher productivity. This situation agrees with the findings of Abu *et al.* (2011), who reported that the average farming experience of sesame farmers in Nasarawa State was 12.8 years. However, access to extension services remains a challenge, as over 80% do not have access to the study area. This is in agreement with Ekunwe *et al.* (2008) who reported that extension services in Nigeria are poorly organized and in some cases, unavailable. About 76.8 % of the respondents had no access to credit while 23.2% had access to credit. This implies that the farmers were using their personal savings to purchase farm inputs and adopt farm innovation. This low access to credit could be attributed to the fact that the government seldomly grants financial credit to large numbers of the farmer. The result agrees with the findings of Onyibe *et al.* (2012) who reported that access to formal credit is a major constraint to sesame farmers in Nigeria.

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Table 1: Socio-economic characteristic of the Farmers

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Gender			
Male	53	64.6	
Female	29	35.4	
Age (years)			
11 - 20	1	1.0	
21 – 30	13	16.0	
31 – 40	39	48.0	
41– 50	19	23.0	
51 – 60	10	12.0	42
Marital status			
Single	19	23.2	
Married	52	63.4	
Widow/widower	11	13.4	
Educational level			
No formal education	8	9.8	
Primary education	12	14.6	
Secondary education	43	52.4	
Tertiary education	19	23.2	
Household size			
1-5	24	29.3	
6-10	46	56.1	
11-15	7	8.5	
16-20	5	6.1	9
Farming experience			
1-5	15	18.3	
6-10	39	47.6	
11-15	21	25.6	
16-20	7	8.5	10
Access to extension services			
Yes	16	19.5	
No	66	80.5	
Membership of cooperative (years)			
Yes	22	26.8	
No	60	73.2	
Access to formal credit			
Yes	19	23.2	
No	63	76.8	
Total	82	100	

Source: field survey, 2018

3.2 Technical Efficiency and its factors of Sesame farmers

Table 2 revealed the estimates of the parameters for the frontier production function and the variance parameters of the model. The variance parameters Sigma (δ^2) was 0.43 and was statistically significant at 1% level of probability. This indicates a good fit and correctness of the distributional form assumed for the composite error term. The value of gamma (γ) is estimated to be 0.94 and it was highly significant at 1% level of probability. This is consistent with the theory that true γ -value should be greater than zero. This implies that 94% of random variation in the yield of the farmers was due to the farmers' inefficiency in their respective sites and not as a result of random variability. Since these factors are under the control of the farmer, reducing the influence of the effect of γ will greatly enhance the technical efficiency of the farmers and improve their yield. This result is consistent with the findings of Omolehin *et al.* (2010) who revealed that about 85% variation in sesame production in Jigawa State is due to inefficiency. The log likelihood function was 0.21. The log likelihood function implies that inefficiency exists in the data set. The log likelihood ratio value represents the value that maximizes the joint densities in the estimated model. However, the estimated coefficients of all the parameters of production function (seed, farm size, labour and herbicide) were positive and significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level of probability and hence play a major role in Sesame production in the study area except fertilizer which is negative and not statistically significant.

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The estimates of the coefficient of the technical inefficiency model are also shown in Table 3. Generally, a negative sign on a parameter means that the variable reduces technical inefficiency, while a positive sign increases technical inefficiency. The coefficient of age, farming experience, household size, access to credit and membership of cooperative (-0.55, -0.61, -0.13, -0.47 and -0.67 respectively), were negative and significant and therefore, increases technical efficiency which agrees with a prior expectation. The coefficient of education (0.89) was positive and significant at 5% level. This indicates that the level of education attained reduces technical efficiency. This implies that a high level of education is not desired for farming of Sesame and indeed, educated people opt for salaried employment in the study area. This result is in agreement with the findings of Usman (2009) among sesame farmers in jigawa state. The coefficient of access to extension service was 0.27 positive and significant at 5% level. The positive sign indicates that not having access to extension service, the greater is the technical inefficiency.

Table 2: Maximum Likelihood Estimates of the Parameters of the stochastic Production Function

Variables	Parameters	Coefficients	t-ratio
Production Factors			
Constant	β_0	0.52183336	0.26808134
Quantity of seed	X_1	0.61013269	2.10428076**
Farm size	X_2	0.40685735	1.65551343***
Total labour input	X_3	0.18204764	2.35299727**
Quantity of herbicide	X_4	0.48437269	4.28483353*
Quantity of fertilizer	X_5	-0.73346438	-0.13091497
Efficiency factors			
Constant	δ_0	0.57484885	0.37355042
Age	Z_1	-0.54503149	-6.14728994*
Level of education	Z_2	0.88524803	2.11595443**
Farming experience	Z_3	-0.61445147	-2.27007668**
Household size	Z_4	-0.12637591	-4.24737279*
Access to extension services	Z_5	0.27173660	2.17068810**
Access to credit	Z_6	-0.46707023	-1.98137312***
Membership of cooperative society	Z_7	-0.67061464	-1.85130021***
Diagnostic Statistics			
Sigma-square	δ^2	0.43046531	0.37757337
Gamma	γ	0.94428077	0.35455549
Log likelihood		0.21273266	
LR test		0.27714749	

***, ** and * denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% levels respectively.

3.3 Frequency Distribution of Technical Efficiency of Sesame Farmers

Table 3 presents the technical efficiency distribution of the Sesame farms in the study area. The mean technical efficiency of the sampled farmers in the study area was 0.81, with 0.97 for the best farmer and 0.31 for the least farmer. This means that on the average, output fell by 19% from the maximum possible level due to inefficiency. 81% of the farmers were predicted to have technical efficiency exceeding 0.31. This indicated that there are some 19% technical inefficient farmers in the study area. This agrees with the findings of Sharon (2016) who reported that the Technical Efficiency (TE) ranged from 0.432 and 0.976 with the mean TE of 0.712, suggests that an average sesame farmer in the study area still has the capacity to increase TE in sesame production by about 28.8% to achieve the maximum possible level while the most efficient one can increase output by 2.4%.The mean technical efficiency is similar to that reported by Maurice (2004) of 80% among cereal crop fadama farmers in Adamawa state in Nigeria.

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Table 3: Distribution of Technical Efficiency of sesame farmers

Class	Frequency	Percentage
0.21-0.40	2	2.4
0.41-0.60	13	15.9
0.61-0.80	28	34.1
0.81-1.00	39	47.6
Total	82	100
Maximum	0.97	
Minimum	0.31	
Mean	0.81	

Source: field survey, 2018

Conclusion and Recommendation

Sesame farmers were found to be technically efficient, but have room for increasing their efficiency by 19%. The study recommends since Sesame farmers do not realize their full production potential, there is a need for sustained improvements on performance through enhanced roles of extension agents by the government in educating farmers on new technologies, which will significantly raise the technical efficiency. Also, the private sector, financial institutions and government should collaborate in assisting farmers in having easy access to credit.

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